

DATA PITCH

Data Pitch will create a transnational, Europe-wide data innovation ecosystem that will bring together data owners and Big Data technology providers, with startups and SMEs with fresh ideas for data-driven products and services.

Data Pitch is an EU Horizon 2020 programme led by the University of Southampton, Open Data Institute, Telecom Italia and Beta-i. **Our goals are to:**

- Explore the critical factors that impact the way organisations create value from sharing data;
- Organise a competition addressing economic, societal, and environmental challenges, present and future, to identify promising digital innovators and data-empowered solutions;
- Create a cross-sectoral, secure data experimentation facility which will offer the winners of this competition a purposeful environment to nurture their ideas; and
- Support them by solving common concerns through funding, technical, legal, marketing, and commercial assistance.

Drawing on the experience from key players in the consortium, we will establish a European Data Innovation Lab, guided and promoted by targeted engagement channels and an international network of hundreds of organisations that have already confirmed their intention to join forces with and support Data Pitch. Together we will make the European data economy stronger and help the region regain leadership in innovation through digital transformation.

PROJECT FACTS AND FIGURES

Project:	GA 732506 - Data Pitch - H2020-ICT-2016-2017/H2020-ICT-2016-1
Coordinator:	University of Southampton, UK
Duration:	36 months from 1 January 2017 to 31 December 2019
Budget:	€7,067,230.00
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